

***N*-Bromonicotinamide – A novel, stable and less expensive oxidant and its antimicrobial activity**

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Abstract : *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN) is prepared by standard procedure and characterized. It is found to be a stable and mild oxidant of low cost. It is prepared by a simple method, giving high yield in a short period of time. The condition and the experimental set up are also very easy to follow. Its formal redox potential shows NBN can be used as effective source of positive halogen. It will be a valuable addition to the existing oxidants. It is screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *Solmonella enterocolitica*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Staphylococcus aureus* at various concentrations using disc diffusion method.

Keywords : *N*-Bromonicotinamide, oxidant.

Recently considerable attention has been focused on the chemistry of *N*-halogeno compounds¹. The diverse nature of the compounds is due to their ability to act as sources of halogenonium cations, hypo halite species and nitrogen anions which act both as bases and nucleophiles. Kinetics of the oxidation of organic compounds by *N*-halogeno amides have received considerable attention². *N*-Bromo compounds have been used as oxidants in kinetic studies for long and in the present work we have used *N*-bromonicotinamide for the first time.

The present paper deals with the synthesis, characterization and usage of NBN for the facile oxidation of organic substrates. This oxidant offers advantages like easy method of synthesis, low cost, low toxicity and mild nature with appreciable stability.

Results and discussion

A plot of E_{obs} against $\log \frac{[\text{NBN}]}{[\text{NA}]}$ from the above equation was made which yield a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1) and the potential from it was calculated to be 0.797 V at 25 °C. This value shows it is a fairly strong oxidizing agent. The value of formal redox potential of the NBN/NA couple viz. (0.797 V at 25 °C) is comparable to the value of +1.14 V for chloramine-T³, +1.16 V for bromamine-T⁴ and +1.02 V for *N*-chloronicotinamide⁵. Redox potential of NBN is 0.797 V at 25 °C whereas that of NCN = 1.02 V. The oxidation of α -

Fig. 1. Determination of E^0 [NBN]/[NA] potentiometrically in a mixture of 0.8 mol dm⁻³ HCl and acetic acid and 50% H₂O (v/v) at 25 °C.

amino acids using NBN is in progress. Considering glycine as the substrate, the rate of oxidation is four times more when we use NBN compared to NCN. k_{obs} for glycine using NBN - $8.88 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, using NCN - $2.11 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. NBN has the following merits over NCN :

- (a) Stability – NBN is fairly stable. Shelf life being almost one year whereas NCN is stable only for

3 months⁵.

- (b) Reactivity – NBN can serve as an efficient reagent for oxidation, halogenation, polymer induced cyclisation, peroxidation, side chain substitution similar to other known *N*-bromo compounds while NCN has been shown to be a mild oxidant.
- (c) Br₂, Br⁺, Br₂⁺, HOBr can be the oxidizing species whereas molecular chlorine is the oxidizing species in NCN.
- (d) ρ value for bromo compounds has been reported even as high as 4 while ρ value does not exceed 0.6 except in the case of NCP (*N*-chlorophthalimide). NCP has ρ value 1.6.
- (e) Selectivity – NBN can be used for a variety of synthetic reactions like *ortho* oxidation, peroxidation, effective oxidation, preferential halogenation while it is of limited applications in the case of chloro compounds.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. All the spectral measurements and elemental analysis were carried out at CDRI, Lucknow using Perkin-Elmer 599, Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer (300 MHz, FT NMR) and for mass spectra Jeol SX-102 (FAB) mass spectrometer.

N-Bromonicotinamide (m.p. 210 °C) was prepared by the method described in literature. 10 g of nicotinamide was added to 150 ml of an ice-cold solution of sodium hypobromite, freshly prepared from 14.4 g (0.09 mol) of bromine, and 9.0 g (0.23 mol) of sodium hydroxide. After shaking for ten minutes, the mixture was filtered rapidly with suction into a cold solution of 9 ml of glacial acetic acid and 25 ml of iced-water. The bromamide which precipitated was filtered off, washed and recrystallized from ethanol (yield 70%) .

Scheme 1

N-Bromonicotinamide : m.p. 210 °C. IR (cm⁻¹) : 1660 (NH), 1530 (CO), 1250 (NBr); ¹H NMR δ : 7.22, 7.39, 7.43 (distorted triplet due to C₅-H), 7.56, 7.62 (due to C₂-H and imido isomers), 7.97, 8.10 [C₄-H broad meta coupling (not resolved)], 8.77, 8.79 (doublet due to C₆-H

next to nitrogen, hump at 9.59 is also due to -NH), 9.09, 9.07 (dd due to CO-NH proton coupled with C₂-H and C₄-H) (Scheme 1); ¹³C NMR δ : 130.0 (C₅), 135.2, 145.0 (due to isomers), 143.6 (C₄), 146.0, 146.4 (C₆), 147.7 (C₂ between nitrogen and carbonyl carbon), 149.4 (C₃), 167.6, 168.5 (due to carbonyl carbon). Elemental analysis : Calcd. (%) for C₆H₅N₂OBr (201) : C, 35.79; H, 2.48; N, 13.91; Br, 39.76; O, 7.95. Found : C, 35.79; H, 3.14; N, 13.27; Br, 39.48; O, 8.40 (oxygen was separately analysed from CDRI, Lucknow). Mass spectral data *m/z* : 124 (due to loss of pyridine), 123 (due to loss of H from CONHBr)⁺•, 201 (molecular ion peak), 203 (M+2 isotopic peak showing the presence of Br atom). Prominent peaks at 89, 77 due to loss of -ONHBr and -CONHBr radicals from the molecular ion⁶. The NBN was found to be soluble in water, acetic acid, sparingly soluble in ethanol but insoluble in CCl₄, CH₂Cl₂ and dioxane. Stock solution of NBN was prepared in 50% acetic acid and water mixture and kept in amber coloured bottle (to prevent interaction with light). It showed no appreciable change in concentration and appearance over a period of one month indicating a fair degree of stability.

A digital potentiometer (Equiptronics dual channel potentiometer EQ-603) with a smooth platinum electrode and a saturated aqueous calomel electrode was used for the determination of formal redox potential of NBN/NA couple.

It involved the measurement of potential in mixtures containing varying concentration ratios of nicotinamide (NA) and NBN in 50% acetic acid and 0.8 mol dm⁻³ HCl keeping the total volume constant at 25 ml. Since dilute solutions of both NA and NBN were used, the activities were replaced by the concentration terms in the Nernst equation

$$E_{\text{obs}} = E^0 + \frac{2.303}{F} RT \log \frac{[\text{NBN}]}{[\text{NA}]}$$

Antimicrobial activity :

The compound was screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *Solmonella enterocolitica*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Staphylococcus aureus* at different concentrations using disc diffusion method⁷. Positive and negative controls were used for comparison. Oxytetracycline disc (Himedia, Mumbai) was used as a positive control, sterile saline (0.85% NaCl solution) was used as negative control. All the observations are given in Table 1.

Bacterial strains used : *E. coli*, *Solmonella enterocolitica*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Staphylococcus aureus*

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of *N*-bromonicotinamide

Bacterium	Minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/disc			
	100	200	400	800
<i>E. coli</i>	-	-	+	++
<i>S. enterocolitica</i>	-	-	-	++
<i>S. flexneri</i>	-	-	-	++
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	-	-	++

(-) No inhibition, (+) zone of inhibition 0-10 mm, (++) zone of inhibition 10-15 mm.

isolated from the clinical sample was used as test organisms. Standard referral *Salmonella typhimurium* strain MTCC 1842 obtained from Microbial Type Culture Collection Centre, Chandigarh was also used for reference purpose.

Preparation of disc : A known quantity of compound NBN was dissolved in water. It was then filtered, sterilized by making use of Sortorius syringe filter of pore size 0.22 µm sterile discs of 6 mm diameter (Hi-Media) were loaded with various concentrations of the compound and dried. Dried discs were stored in sterile containers till use. Solvent loaded discs were also prepared and were used as negative control. Oxytetracycline loaded Hi-Media discs were used as positive control.

Preparation of inoculum :

Clinical isolates and referral strain of *Salmonella typhimurium* strain MTCC 1842 were inoculated in nutrient broth and incubated at 37 °C for four hours in a shaker (Orbitech, Scigenics, India) and was used for antibacterial activity testing and to look for the MIC of various extracts and fractions.

Disc diffusion method was performed to look for the antibacterial activity of various extracts. The assay was performed in triplicates. The zone of inhibition was measured by making use of Tripartigan rule (Hoechst (NCCLS,1993)⁸.

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